

PACIFICUS

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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“LOST DAUGHTER”

The world, a mystery to most,
This young girl found herself lost.
Through time, not one to host,
The daughter couples sought.

Heavy heart through days and more,
Self is the one strength to hold.
Kin often ignore,
This daughter seeking to mold.

Single soul, none on this road,
Silent! Absent! Why, oh Lord?
Your power? This daughter's world?
Lost and ignored!

Yet, You, Mighty King,
Her heart often sings.
She has many to ding,
But her heart knows You are King!
So off she goes, long-lost daughter strums life's string!